

Germination of *M. anisopliae* spores on culture media treated with four fungicides, IIRRI.

Fungicide	Spore germination at 24 h ^a (%)
Benomyl	0 c
Mancozeb	0 c
Thiophanate-methyl	0 c
Mebenil	11 b
Untreated	99 a

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

nation and development. Mebenil was less toxic, allowing 11% germination (see table). Five-day-old cultures of *M. anisopliae* on media treated with fungicide are shown in the figure. Initial tests for direct toxicity of the fungicides to ZLH indicated no effect on the insect. Cages and rice plants used as food should be sprayed with either benomyl, mancozeb, or thiophanate-methyl to increase ZLH survival during mass rearing. □

Growth of green muscardine fungus on media treated with fungicide. Growth is complete on control and partial on mebenil.

Insect pest surveys in Chhatisgarh

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Chhatisgarh is the rice bowl of Madhya Pradesh, with 3.5 million ha under rice cultivation. About 75% is planted to local, tall varieties and 25% is planted to high yielding dwarf varieties such as Phalguna, RPW6-17, Surekha W 13400, Asha R 35-2752, Usha R 35-2750, and Bangoli, all of which are resistant to or tolerant of gall midge (GM). Only 12% of the paddy area has assured irrigation. Annual rainfall is 1,200-1,500 mm and temperature ranges from 11 to 43°C.

Rare rice insect pests at Chhatisgarh, India.

Insect	Abundance (no./hill)	Year
Miridae		
<i>Trigonotylus doddi</i> (Distant)	0-2	1981-82
Lygaeidae		
<i>Cymodema basicornis</i> (Motschulsky)	0-5	1980-82
Curculionidae		
<i>Nanophyes</i> sp. 1	0-5	1980-82
<i>Nanophyes</i> sp. 2	0-2	1981-82
Chrysomelidae		
<i>Cryptocephalus ovulum</i> Suffrian	0-2	1980-83
<i>Cryptocephalus sehestedtii</i> Fabricius	0-2	1980-83
<i>Phyllotreta chotanica</i> Duvivier	5-20	1981-83

In 1980-83, we regularly and intensively surveyed insect pest populations at 10-d intervals in kharif and rabi. In addition to major, commonly observed

rice insects, we found several other insects that caused damage (see table). □

Control of *Metarrhizium anisopliae* in brown planthopper (BPH) rearing

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Metarrhizium anisopliae fungus attacks BPH, green leafhopper (GLH), and zigzag leafhopper in wet season. When infection rate is high, the insect rearing

program for evaluating rice germplasm and breeding lines for hopper resistance is severely disrupted. We evaluated two fungicides for *M. anisopliae* control and their effect on BPH.

To test the effect of fungicides on egg hatching, five gravid females were caged overnight on 30-d-old potted TN1 plants for oviposition. Each plant was

sprayed with 2 ml of a 0.10% spray solution of benomyl, edifenphos, or tap water (control). Nymphs were counted 11 d after oviposition.

The effect of the fungicides on nymphal survival was determined by caging 20 of 2d- and 3d-instar nymphs on 40-d-old potted TN1 plants. At 1, 8, and 15 d after infestation, the